

Kaniadakis Distribution Physically Closer to a Maxwell-Boltzmann at Low e Than the Tsallis?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 17, 2026

The Kaniadakis and Tsallis distributions both have the property that in the large e/T limit, they drop as power laws, i.e. (ke/T) power $1/k$ and $(1-q)e/T$ power $1/(1-q)$. If $1-q = k$, then this is the same power law. Mathematically, both distributions are presented as transforming into the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for $k=0$, or $q=1$. The question we ask is: If physically one is interested in the power law drop-off for $e/T \gg 1$ which is associated with a finite k and a $q \neq 1$, then why would one be at all interested whether the distributions transformed to Maxwell-Boltzmann ones in the $k=0$ or $q=1$ limit?

We try to analyze the situation in the following manner. A finite k or $q \neq 1$ are the physical values of interest, not $k=0$ or $q=1$. This being said, the distribution should not be 0 for $e/T \ll 1$ for physical reasons. If that is the case, one may consider a power law expansion in e/T of some function to the power of $1/k$ (Kaniadakis) or $1/(1-q)$ Tsallis for $e/T \ll 1$. The first term must be a constant, otherwise $e/T=0$ yields 0 for the probability. The second possible term is then constant e/T . If constant $\neq 0$, then in this limit one has $(1 + \text{constant } e/T)$ power $1/k$ or $(1 + \text{constant } e/T)$ power $1/(1-q)$. One may next make the assumption that regardless of the value of k (for finite k) and q (for $q \neq 1$), one should have a distribution that does not depend on the parameter for $e/T \ll 1$. This assumption means that constant $= -k$ for the Kaniadakis case and $-(1-q)$ for the Tsallis and that one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann form $\exp(-e/T)$ in the math limit $e_i/T \rightarrow 0$ for both for $e/T \ll 1$. The question then becomes: Does this have any physical merit? In other words, one tries to assign a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution to a tiny e_i/T which is supposed to approximate 0.

We argue that it does not have much merit for the Tsallis case because the form $\exp(-e/T)$ only holds in the limit of $e/T \ll 1$, but does not allow for any larger range of e/T . On the other hand, the Kaniadakis distribution mimics $\exp(-e/T)$ up to second order in e/T , meaning that the Maxwell-Boltzmann form holds for a larger range of e/T and that there then seems to be some physical basis for it. For the Kaniadakis case, one really does seem to have a physical Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for a small e/T range (for $e/T \ll 1$) as $(e_i/T)(e_i/T)$ and not (e_i/T) is the small number approximating 0. One is not forced to make the cutoff at e/T .

In the Tsallis case, $\exp(-e/T)$ arises simply because one assumes a functional form $1 - e/T$ to first order which could very well match any function with a nonzero first order term. This does not mean that there is actually a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution present. In fact, in the Tsallis case, one uses $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q$, where $p(e_i)$ is the Tsallis distribution, which shows that one has $p(e_i)$ to the power q as being linked with e_i . Thus, physically one does not have an $\exp(-e_i/T)$ Maxwell-Boltzmann scenario except in a very tiny $e/T \ll 1$ limit which one may argue is too small to be really physical.

Power Law Distributions

Physically, dropping power law distributions:

(e_i/T) power $1/k$ or (e_i/T) power $(1/(1-q))$ where $1-q=k$ ((1))

exist in nature. In such a case a nonzero k or $q \neq 1$ matches experimental results. This raises the question: Why would one consider $k=0$ or $q=1$ if the physical values are not $k=0$ and $q=1$? We try to answer this question.

We start by observing that for $e_i=0$, probability would be 0 in ((1)) and that this is likely unphysical. Instead, one should have some function of e_i/T which may be written as a power expansion in e_i/T . If one assumes that the coefficient of e_i/T is nonzero, then:

$(1 + \text{constant } e_i/T)$ power $1/k$ or $(1 + \text{constant } e_i/T)$ power $(1/(1-q))$ ((2))

Including the power implies that the function in () must become e_i/T for $e_i/T \gg 1$ as one must have a dropping power law. Mathematically, $e_i/T \rightarrow \text{tiny number}$ means that $1 + \text{constant } e_i/T \rightarrow \exp(\text{constant } e_i/T)$. If one assumes that in the tiny e_i/T limit there is no effect of k or q on the probability, then:

Constant = $-k$ or $-(1-q)$ ((3))

in order to have a decrease in probability with e_i for e_i/T very small. The point is that ((3)) leads to the probability:

$\exp(-e_i/T)$ ((4))

Is the tiny e_i/T limit simply a math limit or is there any physicality to the resulting Maxwell-Boltzmann form? The real Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution holds for all e_i/T values not only for a very tiny e_i/T .

We suggest that in the Tsallis case, the distribution only becomes a Maxwell-Boltzmann one in the tiny e_i/T limit and that this seems to be a math limit. On the other hand, the Kaniadakis distribution mimics $\exp(-e_i/T)$ to second order in e_i/T so we argue there is reason to believe that a physical Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution exists for a slightly larger range of e_i/T , i.e it is $(e_i/T)(e_i/T)$ which is the "tiny" number and not e_i/T (even though e_i/T is still small). We next consider the explicit forms of the two distributions to show this.

Kaniadakis and Tsallis Distributions

The Tsallis distribution is:

$p(e_i/T) = (1 - (1-q)e_i/T)$ power $1/(1-q)$ ((5)) (unnormalized)

In the tiny e_i/T limit, the distribution only matches $\exp(-e_i/T)$ to first order in e_i/T . This means that e_i/T is associated with the math limit of becoming zero and there is not much physical basis for assuming a Maxwell-Boltzmann in anything more than a math form in the $e_i/T \rightarrow 0$ limit. Practically, however, e_i/T may have a small value and one might somehow consider a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution existing in this very restricted region.

One may note that the Tsallis distribution is associated with the energy average $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ power q and so one has a power law of $p(e_i)$ which is already physically different from the Maxwell-Boltzmann approach of $p(e_i)$ with power 1. For $e_i/T \ll 1$, $p(e_i)$ power q has the form $1 + \text{constant } e_i/T$, but the constant involves q which is not the physical Maxwell-Boltzmann case, but rather a math limit.

The Kaniadakis distribution is

$$p(e_i) = \{ \sqrt{1 + k e_i/T} - k e_i/T \}^{\text{power } 1/k} \quad ((6)) \quad (\text{unnormalized})$$

In this case, a low e_i/T expansion yields:

$$p(e_i) = \{ 1 - x + .5 x^2 \}^{\text{power } 1/k} \quad \text{where } x = e_i/T \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{One may note that } \exp(-e_i/T) = 1 - e_i/T + .5 (e_i/T)(e_i/T) + \dots \quad ((8))$$

As a result, the Kaniadakis distribution mimics the physical Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution up to second order in e_i/T , which means that it is not simply a Maxwell-Boltzmann in the $e_i/T \rightarrow 0$ limit. It seems that in the Kaniadakis case there really is a physical Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution existing for a small e_i/T range which is larger than the usual math limit $e_i/T \rightarrow 0$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the mathematical statement that a Tsallis distribution becomes a Maxwell-Boltzmann one for $q=1$ and the Kaniadakis, for $k=0$ is really linked to $e_i/T \ll 1$ considerations. Both distributions become e_i/T power $1/k$ or e_i/T power $1/(1-q)$ for $e_i/T \ll 1$ and k is not 0 or $q \neq 1$ in order to match experimental data. If this is the case, why would one be interested in $k=0$ or $q=1$ as they are not physical? We argue that it is the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit that is of concern. (e_i/T) power $1/k$ is 0 for $e_i=0$, but this is probably unphysical. One should have finite probability for e_i/T small. This means considering a function $f(e_i/T)$ such that in the $e_i/T \rightarrow$ tiny number limit one has: $(1 + \text{constant } e_i/T)$ power $1/k$. (Note: For the Tsallis case, $1/k$ is replaced with $1/(1-q)$). if one assumes that constant $\neq 0$. If one further assumes that the dropping power parameter k or q has nothing to do with the probability for $e_i/T \ll 1$, then constant = $-k e_i/T$ or $-(1-q) e_i/T$ in the $e_i/T \rightarrow 0$ limit. This leads to the math form $\exp(-e_i/T)$ in the $\lim e_i/T \rightarrow 0$. Usually one approximates this limit by a tiny e_i/T value and so we argue that there is really no reason to expect that there is much of a physical Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution present. This is the situation in the Tsallis case as the distribution is: $\{ 1 - (1-q)e_i/T \}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)}$.

In the Kaniadakis case, however, $p(e_i) = \{ \sqrt{1 + k e_i/T} - k e_i/T \}^{\text{power } 1/k}$ becomes $\{ 1 - k e_i/T + .5 k^2 e_i^2/T^2 \}^{\text{power } 1/k}$. This approximates a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution (albeit with k factor present) for a larger range of e_i/T as $(e_i/T)(e_i/T)$ is the "tiny" number. We argue that one may consider a physical Maxwell-Boltzmann present in the Kaniadakis case as it holds for more than the limit $e_i/T \rightarrow 0$ (and its approximation e_i/T). Here e_i/T does not need to go to zero as it is $(e_i/T)(e_i/T)$ which approximates 0.